

A3

A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI PADOVA

CAB CENTRO DI ATENEIO
PER LE BIBLIOTECHE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536

Version 1.0

July 2023

A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects

A₃ / CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies

Cristiana Bettella¹, Mauro Apostolico¹, Linda Cappellato¹, Yuri Carrer¹,
Achille Felicetti², Giulio Turetta¹

¹ University of Padua

² Polo Universitario Città di Prato

Dissemination Level of the Document

Public

Abstract

In order to better define a citation model for cultural heritage objects and to formulate concrete proposals for its application, three digital repositories were selected as case studies: Archaeological Data Service (ADS), Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI), and Phaidra - University of Padua.

To this end, a descriptive model specifically designed to meet semantic citation criteria from a *cit(ation)-actionability* perspective was defined and implemented to collect relevant information about the repositories under study and their data citation practices. The model is available as an annex to this document.

The citation records currently used by the selected repositories were illustrated and discussed on the basis of some example data objects, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses identified in terms of semantic reference to cultural heritage objects. This is followed by suggestions for the improvement of the repository citation model.

Version history

Version	Date	Authors/Contributors	Description
V1.0	28/07/2023	Cristiana Bettella, Mauro Apostolico, Linda Cappellato, Yuri Carrer, Achille Felicetti, Giulio Turetta	

Copyright notice

Some rights reserved ©2023 University of Padua, except where noted otherwise. This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). This license is not applied to images with different owners.

Cover image: Gino Morandi (Morandis), Fresco at the entrance of Morgagni Hall at the University of Padua Hospital (detail). © 1964 Gino Morandi / © 2023 University of Padua.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
2. Rationale.....	5
3. Methodology.....	5
4. Archaeology Data Service (ADS): Case study.....	7
4.1 General.....	7
4.2 Data Citation.....	13
4.3 Findings and Discussion.....	15
4.3.1 Common findings.....	15
4.3.2 Use cases.....	15
5. Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI): Case study.....	21
5.1 General.....	21
5.2 Data Citation.....	26
5.3 Findings and Discussion.....	28
5.3.1 Use cases.....	28
6. Phaidra - University of Padua: Case study.....	35
6.1 General.....	35
6.2 Data Citation.....	40
6.3 Findings and Discussion.....	41
6.3.1 Critical citation elements.....	42
6.3.2 Citation record example.....	44
6.3.3 Use cases.....	44
Annexes.....	53
CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies. Template.....	53
General.....	53
Data Citation.....	58
Use case.....	60

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
ARK	Archival Resource Key
CHO	Cultural Heritage Object
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
DC	Dublin Core
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
ISMI	International Standard Manuscript Identifier
ISWC	International Standard Musical Work Code
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PURL	Persistent Uniform Resource Locator
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
ROR	Research Organization Registry
TDR	Trusted Digital Repository
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
VIAF	Virtual International Authority File

1. Introduction

Defining the critical citation elements of a cultural heritage object (CHO) constitutes one of the key activities of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects* and represents the foundational core upon which the establishment of the citation model is hinged.

In accordance with a methodological approach based on applied qualitative analysis, a model for detecting the citation specifications of a digital repository has been specifically designed to meet semantic citation criteria from a *cit(ation)-actionability* perspective.

The model was applied to three digital archives, selected as case studies according to the conceptual framework of the project, primarily the cross-disciplinarity of cultural heritage, the correlation with projects and lines of research related to RDA activities, the CHO citation as a FAIR-enabling essential constituent of information integration with reference to both EOSC and the Common European data space for cultural heritage, as well as the future European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage.

Each case study was shared with the representatives of the individual repositories with a twofold purpose: on the one hand, to critically evaluate the model crafted for the analysis of citation specifications and, on the other hand, as a preliminary assessment of the level of citability of cultural objects according to the citation model in current use or in the perspective of implementation.

The aim of the following deliverable is to document the rationale and the methodology adopted, the process of analysis, the data collected and the analytical discussion of the findings for each of the case studies examined.

2. Rationale

Analyse and discuss the citation models currently in use in three digital cultural heritage repositories selected as case studies. This examination is grounded in a specially developed data collection model which aims to identify and label data citation descriptors, while providing the basis for an in-depth analysis of citation practices in the repositories studied.

3. Methodology

In order to better define the CHO citation model and formulate concrete proposals for its application, we selected three digital repositories as case studies: Archaeological Data Service (ADS)¹, Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI)², and Phaidra - University of Padua³.

A descriptive model specifically designed to meet semantic citation criteria from a *cit(ation)-actionability* perspective was developed to capture relevant information about the repositories under study and their data citation practices. The case study model is built on a specific methodology that aims to identify and label the descriptors involved in the analysis of the citation model of a research data repository. This template is also annexed to the present document.

On the basis of these criteria, three case study documents have been crafted comprising the identification of data citation descriptors that inform the basis for an in-depth analysis of citation practices in the repositories under study.

Furthermore, using some example data objects hosted by the repositories, the citation records currently in use by the repositories were illustrated and discussed, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses identified in terms of semantic reference to cultural heritage objects. Suggestions are then made for improving the repository citation model.

The following general principles underlie the analysis of the sample citation records:

- A citation model for CHOs is the conflation of cultural heritage object and digital representation in such a way that those who cite or use the citation can transparently understand what each component of the citation refers to.
- If the act of citation occurs in the context of a collection of data or a complex citation context, the context may provide a source for the citation.
- A citation model for CHOs always refers to both the CHO and its digital representation, and consistently uses events, relationships, properties to relate to the “objects in the middle” in

¹ <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/>

² <https://dri.ie/>

³ <https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/>

the citation. For instance, to cite the digitisation of a photograph of a painting, the citation will reflect a component part about the painting, a component part about the digitisation, and then use a property to add information pertaining to the photograph that describes the event of digitisation.

- A citation model for CHOs can make use of ontologies or semantic qualifications to make the citation components explicit when appropriate.

The DRI and ADS case studies, including the data collected and the proposed semantic enrichment of the citation model in accordance with the model described above, have been submitted for review by the principal staff members⁴ of the respective repositories and are reported as such, together with the comments gathered, in this document⁵. As already mentioned, this preliminary consultation was also intended to be a general assessment of the methodology adopted for the case study on the citation models of the selected repositories.

Finally, it should be emphasised that the analysis carried out on Phaidra - University of Padua, which currently lacks a data citation functionality, has led to the exploratory design of a citation model that will be implemented as a new feature within the development activities planned for this repository, in close coherence with the work in progress to define “A FAIR-enabling citation model for cultural heritage objects”.

⁴ We would like to take this opportunity to express our special thanks to Joan Murphy and Beth Knazook and the whole team at DRI, Tim Evans and Julian D. Richards at ADS, for the willingness and interest they have shown in our work, and for their fundamental cooperation in supporting the case study analysis process.

⁵ Shared on 5/07/2023 (DRI) and 22/07/2023 (ADS) respectively. The DRI case study was discussed in a dedicated virtual meeting attended by the DRI team on 18/07/2023. The analysis of DRI use cases is based on examples from the DRI collections provided by DRI on 13/04/2023 along with explanations of the most significant issues. It is important to note that in the case of the DRI, the revision of the citation model is also at the heart of an ongoing analysis being undertaken in the context of the European WorldFAIR project, of which the DRI is leading the Cultural Heritage Case Study (<https://worldfair-project.eu/cultural-heritage/>). In particular, the citation model has been identified as one of the recommendations discussed in the WorldFAIR Project Deliverable (D13.2) *Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report* (see: Knazook, Beth, Murphy, Joan, Barner, Keren, Cassidy, Kathryn, Claeysens, Steven, Cortese, Claudio, Manchester, Eileen J., et al. “Worldfair Project (D13.2) Cultural Heritage Image Sharing Recommendations Report”. Zenodo, May 19, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7897244>, p. 15-17). As far as ADS is concerned, a virtual meeting is planned for September (2023) to discuss a possible proposal to further develop the current citation model. This activity is closely related to the ongoing development aimed at enhancing the FAIRness of the repository, while demonstrating how a semantically designed citation model can act as an essential FAIR-enabling driver.

4. Archaeology Data Service (ADS): Case study

The ADS is an accredited digital repository for heritage data that supports research, learning and teaching with freely available, high quality and dependable digital resources by preserving and disseminating digital data in the long term. The ADS also promotes good practice in the use of digital data, provides technical advice to the heritage community, and supports the deployment of digital technologies.

Description of the research data repository from its [re3data.org record](#).

4.1 General

Repository Name <i>r3d:repositoryName - The full name of the research data repository.</i>	Archaeology Data Service
Repository URL <i>r3d:repositoryUrl - The URL of the research data repository.</i>	https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/
Repository identifier <i>r3d:repositoryIdentifier - A globally unique identifier that refers to the research data repository or a record describing the research data repository.</i> The URI of the research data repository identifier (DOI, ROR, RRID, Handle, etc.).	https://ror.org/04w1khd64 http://isni.org/isni/0000000107410297 https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q4785478
Repositories registry records The URLs of the research data repository record in the re3data.org , FAIRsharing.org , OpenDOAR repositories registry.	re3data.org: http://doi.org/10.17616/R3MW23 FAIRsharing.org: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hm1mfq OpenDOAR: https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/1578
Provider type <i>r3d:providerType - The type of provider.</i>	Data provider Service provider
Data provider for aggregator/catalogue	Europeana < https://www.europeana.eu > ARIADNE Portal < https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/ >

<p><i>The aggregator or catalogue services the research data repository provides the research data.</i></p> <p>Catalogue/aggregator name and catalogue/aggregator home page URL, or Unknown.</p>	<p>Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN) data portal <https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php></p> <p>Heritage Gateway <https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/gateway/default.aspx></p> <p>DataCite <https://datacite.org/></p> <p>Keepers Registry <https://keepers.issn.org/></p> <p>Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) data discovery portal <https://data-search.nerc.ac.uk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/home></p>
<p>Subjects</p> <p><i>r3d:subject - The disciplinary focus of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Archaeology</p> <p>Humanities</p> <p>Prehistory</p> <p>Natural Science</p> <p>History</p> <p>Ancient Cultures</p>
<p>Persistent identifier systems</p> <p><i>r3d:pidSystem - The persistent identifier system that is used/provided by the research data repository for research data.</i></p> <p>The PID systems provided by the research data repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DOI ● Handle ● ARK ● PURL ● URN ● Other (provide related URL) <p>Provide also the registration authority (if known).</p>	<p>DOI</p>
<p>Policy</p>	<p>Preservation policy <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/policies/ads-policies-and-procedures/preservation-policy></p>

<p><i>r3d:policy</i> - Policies providing information concerning the usage of the research data repository.</p> <p>The policy title and URL of the data curation policy, sustainability policy, data quality policy, etc.</p> <p>The data citation policy should be stated in the "Data Citation" section of the template.</p>	<p>y/></p> <p>Metadata policy and procedures <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/policies/metadata/></p> <p>Access and reuse of data <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/policies/use-access-to-data/></p> <p>Rights management framework <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/policies/rights-management-framework/></p>
<p>Repository certification</p> <p><i>r3d:certificate</i> - The certificate, accreditation or standard the research data repository complies with.</p> <p>The certificate name, URL, year of accreditation and validity period.</p>	<p>CoreTrustSeal <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Archaeology-Data-Service.pdf>, 2020. Renewal is under review.</p>
<p>Data model</p> <p>Brief description of the data model and/or related documentation URL.</p>	<p>The content of ADS is organised around four top-level concepts:</p> <p>WHAT: search by type of objects, such as sites, monuments or artefacts. It also includes types of interventions, such as archaeological excavations, field surveys and remote sensing investigations.</p> <p>WHERE: geographical search based on the place where the research, investigation or other archaeological activities were carried out. It concerns specific English regions and sites.</p> <p>WHEN: time-based search, essentially using archaeological periods such as Prehistoric, Roman, and Medieval.</p> <p>RESOURCE: search by aggregated content provider primarily understood as the organisation or institution that created the aggregated record from ADS.</p> <p>The data is mainly structured using Dublin Core and can also be consulted through an OAI-PMH endpoint.</p> <p>As it is evident by consulting the OAI-PMH endpoint, specific fields of the Dublin Core format are used to expose the four main categories, i.e., the dc:creator field is used to build up the</p>

RESOURCE concept; dc:subject is used to classify the data related to WHAT, the dc:coverage field (with type= "temporal") for WHEN and (with type="spatial") for WHERE; the dc:relation field is used for bibliography and other related information, and so on.

The main objects in ADS belong to three resource types:

- Records: geographic location oriented, briefly describe archaeological events, monuments or sites.
- Archives: archaeological data-oriented (with rich metadata)
- Library: bibliographic catalogue (topic-oriented)

For example, reports can be found using Library and Archives.

Search & Browse

There are several search patterns for users:

- Search the records
 - Find basic record
- Search the records
 - Find an archive -> Browse and search in the archive
- Search the library
 - Find a Report -> Go to the archive the report belongs to

Finds can be included in Archives and can be searched/browsed only inside the archive but the record search can include the object type, period, material type and link to the archive. For example, <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/archsearch/browser.xhtml>.

WHAT > Object Types > Container > Currency > Coin Blank > will find the record > archive > https://www.heritagegateway.org.uk/Gateway/Results_Single.aspx?uid=1152845&resourceID=19191 about the Coin Blank.

Queries can be done using the standard OAI-PMH features, for example, <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/oai/archives/OAIHandler?verb=ListSets> to list all the available sets, or <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/oai/archives/>

	<p>OAIHandler?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_dc&set=ALL to browse a specific set (in this case the "ALL" one).</p> <p>Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project/Resource/File metadata <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/help-guidance/guides-to-good-practice/the-project-lifecycle/project-metadata/> • Collection metadata <https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/help-guidance/instructions-for-depositors/collection-level-metadata/>
<p>Resource types</p> <p><i>r3d:contentType</i> - All types of resources available in the research data repository.</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1.</p>	<p>Image <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_c513></p> <p>Text <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_18cf></p> <p>Video <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_12ce></p> <p>Dataset <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_ddb1></p> <p>Other (3D object) <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_1843></p>
<p>Metadata standards</p> <p><i>r3d:metadataStandard</i> - The metadata standard the research data repository complies with.</p> <p>Standard name and URI from the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (preferable) or the Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications, or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dublin Core <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15></p> <p>PREMIS Ontology <https://bartoc.org/en/node/18191></p>
<p>Object landing page metadata qualification</p> <p><i>Machine-readable metadata provided in the object landing page of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Possible values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schema.org • Dublin Core • EPrints metadata • Highwire Press metadata 	<p>Open Graph metadata</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Graph metadata • Signposting Typed Links • Other (provide related URL) 	
<p>Semantic artefacts integration</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefacts the research data repository supports in the object's metadata.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Library of Congress Subject Headings <http://bartoc.org/en/node/454></p> <p>Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names <http://bartoc.org/en/node/109></p> <p>Other - UK Heritage thesauri <https://www.heritagedata.org/blog/vocabularies-provided/></p> <p>Other - PREMIS Data Dictionary <https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/v3/></p> <p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p>
<p>Versioning</p> <p><i>r3d:versioning - The research data repository supports versioning of research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Data access rights</p> <p><i>r3d:dataAccessType - The access regulation to the research data sets provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI from COAR Access Rights Vocabulary 1.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>open access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2></p>
<p>Data rights</p> <p><i>The applicable rights to the research data in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI of data rights available in the research data repository from the RightsStatements.org list or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/</p>
<p>Data licences</p> <p><i>r3d:dataLicense - The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for research data.</i></p>	<p>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>Open Government Licence v3.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/OGDL-UK-3.0.html></p>

License name and URI from the SPDX Licence List or Other (provide related URL).	Other - ADS Standard Terms of Use and Access < https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/about/policies/use-access-to-data/ads-terms-of-use-and-access/ >
<p>Metadata licences</p> <p><i>The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for the research objects metadata.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX License List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal <https://spdx.org/licenses/CCo-1.0.html></p>

Table 1: General section of ADS case study.

4.2 Data Citation

Considering the rich data model, we take into account the data citation on Archives datasets only, which has the richest and most complex representation.

<p>Data citation policy</p> <p><i>r3d:citationGuidelineUrl - The URL of the policy outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>ADS FAQs - "How do I cite ADS data" https://archaeologydataservice.ac.uk/help-guidance/faqs/</p>
<p>Endorsed data citation recommendations</p> <p><i>Data citation recommendations the repository endorses in the data citation policy.</i></p> <p>Data citation recommendation title and URL.</p>	<p>Not available</p>
<p>"Cite as" feature</p> <p><i>An automatic feature the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Data citation styles</p>	<p>ADS Archives: Custom - ADS (based on DataCite citation format)</p>

<p><i>The citation styles the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>Available citation styles in the “Cite as” feature of the research data repository, and the citation style tools implemented (e.g. Citation Style Language processor “citeproc-js”).</p>	
<p>Data citation record elements</p> <p><i>Critical citation elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Citation element and citation element property in the citation record.</p>	<p>Title [Mandatory]</p> <p>Creator [Mandatory]</p> <p>Date issued [Mandatory]</p> <p>Resource type [Mandatory]</p> <p>Location (DOI) [Mandatory]</p> <p>Host location [Mandatory]</p> <p>Host name (distributor) [Mandatory]</p>
<p>Data citation record syntax</p> <p><i>The data citation record format the research data repository provides to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>The element names comprised in the data citation record in the format and order the research data repository provides.</p>	<p>Creator (Date issued) Title [Resource type], Host location: Host name [<i>Distributor</i>] DOI</p>
<p>Data citation record semantics</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefact elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p>

Table 2: Data Citation section of ADS case study.

4.3 Findings and Discussion

The underlying idea is to identify the cultural object (e.g., the archaeological site) to which the Archives datasets relate.

We propose a citation record that comprises the digital object (e.g., an Archive “dataset”) and the reference to the cultural heritage object.

4.3.1 Common findings

The citation indications are provided explicitly through the “How to cite using this DOI” feature available on the landing page of the Archive.

The elements included in the citation are not exhaustive enough for the identification and citation attribution of the cultural object. For example, the Archive [HMJ Underhill Archive](#) refers to Stonehenge, but there is no reference in the citation as it focuses on the Archive itself.

4.3.2 Use cases

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>Petrography, Geochemistry and Mineralogy of the Stonehenge Sarsens: Digital Data Collection</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5284/1084808</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dataset</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Image</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Data (information)</p> <p><http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300312038></p> <p>Digital information</p> <p><http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300380412></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>54 %, https://f-ujl.net/view/410 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p> <p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	<p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://doi.org/10.5284/1084808</p>
<p>Citation record</p>	<p>David Nash, Jake Ciborowski, Tobias Salge, Magret Damaschke, Steven Goderis (2021) Petrography, Geochemistry and Mineralogy of the Stonehenge</p>

<p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>Sarsens: Digital Data Collection [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] https://doi.org/10.5284/1084808</p>
--	---

Table 3: Use case 1 of ADS case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

The main issue is that information on the cultural heritage object represented (e.g., Stonehenge) is missing.

We expand the Archive citation record adding a qualified relationship to the cultural heritage object (CHO), the CHO persistent identifier, and the title of the CHO (hyper)linked to the CHO GeoNames identifier if available. The association between the title and GeoNames URI is implemented using the same mechanism used to link the authors' name and the DOI.

Proposed citation

[David Nash](#), [Jake Ciborowski](#), [Tobias Salge](#), [Magret Damaschke](#), [Steven Goderis](#) (2021) Petrography, Geochemistry and Mineralogy of the Stonehenge Sarsens: Digital Data Collection [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] <https://doi.org/10.5284/1084808> [analysis of] <https://viaf.org/viaf/137120591> [Stonehenge]

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>Laser Scan Data from Norwich Cathedral, Norwich, Norfolk 2019</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.5284/1091202</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dataset</p> <p>Image</p> <p>Other (3D object)</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Data (information) <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300312038></p> <p>Digital information <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300380412></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p><i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i></p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>52 %, https://www.f-ujl.net/view/417 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p> <p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	<p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?chema_url=https://doi.org/10.5284/1091202</p>
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>Nicholas Webb, Alexandrina Buchanan, Sarah Duffy, James Hillson, JR Peterson (2021) <i>Laser Scan Data from Norwich Cathedral, Norwich, Norfolk 2019</i> [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] https://doi.org/10.5284/1091202</p>

Table 4: Use case 2 of ADS case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

The main issue is that information on the cultural heritage object represented (e.g., Norwich Cathedral) needs to be included in the citation.

Moreover, it needs to be clarified what the date “2021” refers to. In the Archive metadata the first released date recorded is “2022”. This might be due to human error in the compilation of metadata.

Proposed citation

Nicholas Webb, Alexandrina Buchanan, Sarah Duffy, James Hillson, JR Peterson (2021) Laser Scan Data from Norwich Cathedral, Norwich, Norfolk 2019 [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] <https://doi.org/10.5284/1091202> [3D scan of] <https://viaf.org/viaf/273148995794859751030> [Norwich Cathedral]

Use case name	Archaeology at Glastonbury Abbey on-line
Example object <i>The example object to review.</i> The URL of the example object (PID preferable).	https://doi.org/10.5284/1000292
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Dataset Image Text
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Data (information) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300312038 > Digital information < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300380412 > Reports < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300027267 > Photographs < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300046300 > Computer drawings < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300076598 > Drawings (visual works) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300033973 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	56 %, https://f-uji.net/view/421 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i>	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://doi.org/10.5284/1000292

<p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>Trustees of Glastonbury Abbey (2010) Archaeology at Glastonbury Abbey on-line [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] https://doi.org/10.5284/1000292</p>

Table 5: Use case 3 of ADS case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

The main issue is that information on the cultural heritage object represented (e.g., Glastonbury Abbey) needs to be included in the citation.

Proposed citation

Trustees of Glastonbury Abbey (2010) Archaeology at Glastonbury Abbey on-line [data-set]. York: Archaeology Data Service [distributor] <https://doi.org/10.5284/1000292> [analysis of] <https://viaf.org/viaf/134870077> [Glastonbury Abbey]

5. Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI): Case study

The Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI) is a national trusted digital repository (TDR) for Ireland’s social and cultural data. We preserve, curate, and provide sustained access to a wealth of Ireland’s humanities and social sciences data through a single online portal. The repository houses unique and important collections from a variety of organisations including higher education institutions, cultural institutions, government agencies, and specialist archives.

DRI has staff members from a wide variety of backgrounds, including software engineers, designers, digital archivists and librarians, data curators, policy and requirements specialists, educators, project managers, social scientists and humanities scholars. DRI is certified by the CoreTrustSeal, the current TDR standard widely recommended for best practice in Open Science.

In addition to providing trusted digital repository services, the DRI is also Ireland’s research centre for best practices in digital archiving, repository infrastructures, preservation policy, research data management and advocacy at the national and European levels.

DRI contributes to policy making nationally (e.g. via the National Open Research Forum and the IRC), and internationally, including European Commission expert groups, the DPC, RDA and the OECD.

Description of the research data repository from its [re3data.org record](https://re3data.org/record/).

5.1 General

<p>Repository Name</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryName - The full name of the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>Digital Repository of Ireland</p>
<p>Repository URL</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryUrl - The URL of the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>https://repository.dri.ie/</p>
<p>Repository identifier</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryIdentifier - A globally unique identifier that refers to the research data repository or a record describing the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The URI of the research data repository identifier (DOI, ROR, RRID, Handle, etc.).</p>	<p>https://ror.org/034d7ma87</p> <p>https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q47461569</p>

<p>Repositories registry records</p> <p>The URLs of the research data repository record in the re3data.org, FAIRsharing.org, OpenDOAR repositories registry.</p>	<p>re3data.org: http://doi.org/10.17616/R3W632</p> <p>FAIRsharing.org: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.wL29nJ</p> <p>OpenDOAR: https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/10062</p>
<p>Provider type</p> <p><i>r3d:providerType - The type of provider.</i></p>	<p>Data provider</p> <p>Service provider</p>
<p>Data provider for aggregator/catalogue</p> <p><i>The aggregator or catalogue services the research data repository provides the research data.</i></p> <p>Catalogue/aggregator name and catalogue/aggregator home page URL, or Unknown.</p>	<p>Europeana <https://www.europeana.eu></p> <p>DataCite <https://datacite.org/></p>
<p>Subjects</p> <p><i>r3d:subject - The disciplinary focus of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Social and Behavioural Sciences</p> <p>Natural Science</p> <p>Earth Science</p> <p>Geography</p> <p>Humanities and Social Sciences</p> <p>Humanities</p> <p>Human Geography</p> <p>Social Science</p> <p>Education Science</p> <p>Theology</p> <p>Literary Studies</p> <p>Ancient Cultures</p> <p>Art History</p> <p>Fine Arts</p> <p>Musicology</p> <p>Theatre Studies</p>

	Media Studies
<p>Persistent identifier systems</p> <p><i>r3d:pidSystem - The persistent identifier system that is used/provided by the research data repository for research data.</i></p> <p>The PID systems provided by the research data repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Handle • ARK • PURL • URN • Other (provide related URL) <p>Provide also the registration authority (if known).</p>	<p>DOI (DataCite)</p>
<p>Policy</p> <p><i>r3d:policy - Policies providing information concerning the usage of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The policy title and URL of the data curation policy, sustainability policy, data quality policy, etc.</p> <p>The data citation policy should be stated in the "Data Citation" section of the template.</p>	<p>DRI Preservation Policy <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.2r377c523></p> <p>DRI Collection Policy <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.kk91v774c></p> <p>DRI Policy Framework 2012-02 - 2019-04 <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.qz2167463-1></p> <p>DRI Restricted Data Policy (Amended 2019) <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.8623xk58w></p>
<p>Repository certification</p> <p><i>r3d:certificate - The certificate, accreditation or standard the research data repository complies with.</i></p> <p>The certificate name, URL, year of accreditation and validity period.</p>	<p>CoreTrustSeal <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/20211026-digital-repository-of-ireland_final.pdf>, 2021 (valid until 2024-10-28).</p>
<p>Data model</p> <p>Brief description of the data model and/or related documentation URL.</p>	<p>Documentation: https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.qr474f68n</p>

<p>Resource types</p> <p><i>r3d:contentType</i> - All types of resources available in the research data repository.</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1.</p>	<p>Image</p> <p>Sound</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Text</p> <p>Dataset</p> <p>Other (3D object)</p>
<p>Metadata standards</p> <p><i>r3d:metadataStandard</i> - The metadata standard the research data repository complies with.</p> <p>Standard name and URI from the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (preferable) or the Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications, or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dublin Core <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15></p> <p>MODS <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m97></p> <p>MARCXML <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m88></p> <p>EAD <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m96></p>
<p>Object landing page metadata qualification</p> <p><i>Machine-readable metadata provided in the object landing page of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Possible values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schema.org • Dublin Core • EPrints metadata • Highwire Press metadata • Open Graph metadata • Signposting Typed Links • Other (provide related URL) 	<p>Open Graph metadata</p>
<p>Semantic artefacts integration</p> <p><i>The semantic artefacts the research data repository supports in the object's metadata.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>LCSH <http://bartoc.org/en/node/454></p> <p>LCNAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/18536></p> <p>AAT <http://bartoc.org/en/node/75></p> <p>HASSET <http://bartoc.org/en/node/19></p> <p>HOMOSAURUS <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1761></p>

	<p>periodO <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1683></p> <p>Unesco <http://bartoc.org/en/node/40></p>
<p>Versioning</p> <p><i>r3d:versioning - The research data repository supports versioning of research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Data access rights</p> <p><i>r3d:dataAccessType - The access regulation to the research data sets provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI from COAR Access Rights Vocabulary 1.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>embargoed access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_f1cf></p> <p>open access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2></p> <p>restricted access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_16ec></p>
<p>Data rights</p> <p><i>The applicable rights to the research data in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI of data rights available in the research data repository from the RightsStatements.org list or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>In Copyright <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/></p> <p>In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-EDU/1.0/></p> <p>Orphan Work <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-OW-EU/1.0/></p>
<p>Data licences</p> <p><i>r3d:dataLicense - The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for research data.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX Licence List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>CC BY 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-SA 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-ND 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-ND-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html></p> <p>Open Data Commons Open Database License v1.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/ODbL-1.0.html></p> <p>Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/ODC-By-1.0.html></p>

	<p>Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal <https://spdx.org/licenses/CCo-1.0.html></p> <p>Other - Public Domain Mark 1.0 <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/></p> <p>Other - Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL) v1.0 <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/pddl/1-0/></p>
<p>Metadata licences</p> <p><i>The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for the research objects metadata.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX License List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>CC BY 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal <https://spdx.org/licenses/CCo-1.0.html></p>

Table 6: General section of DRI case study.

5.2 Data Citation

<p>Data citation policy</p> <p><i>r3d:citationGuidelineUrl - The URL of the policy outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.rx91h486p</p>
<p>Endorsed data citation recommendations</p> <p><i>Data citation recommendations the repository endorses in the data citation policy.</i></p> <p>Data citation recommendation title and URL.</p>	<p>CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices, Out of Cite, Out of Mind: The Current State of Practice, Policy, and Technology for the Citation of Data <https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf></p> <p>UK Data Archive, Data Citation. What you need to know <http://ukdataservice.ac.uk/media/104397/data_citation_online.pdf></p>
<p>“Cite as” feature</p> <p><i>An automatic feature the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>

<p>Data citation styles</p> <p><i>The citation styles the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>Available citation styles in the “Cite as” feature of the research data repository, and the citation style tools implemented (e.g. Citation Style Language processor “citeproc-js”).</p>	<p>APA</p> <p>MLA</p> <p>Chicago</p> <p>Custom - DRI (using citeproc-ruby CSL processor)</p>
<p>Data citation record elements</p> <p><i>Critical citation elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Citation element and citation element property in the citation record.</p>	<p>Creator [Mandatory]</p> <p>Publication Date [Mandatory]</p> <p>Title [Mandatory]</p> <p>Publisher [Optional]</p> <p>Publisher/Host [Mandatory] (Distributor and Depositing Institution)</p> <p>Location [Mandatory] (DOI)</p>
<p>Data citation record syntax</p> <p><i>The data citation record format the research data repository provides to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>The element names comprised in the data citation record in the format and order the research data repository provides.</p>	<p>Creator (Publication Date) Title, Publisher, Distributor Name [<i>Distributor</i>], Depositing Institution Name [<i>Depositing Institution</i>], DOI</p>
<p>Data citation record semantics</p> <p><i>The semantic artefact elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>

Table 7: Data Citation section of DRI case study.

5.3 Findings and Discussion

The citation indications are explicitly provided through the “Cite” function available on the landing page of the object.

In all the use cases, we found an issue with the value of the “date” element in the data citation. DRI uses the collection date – i.e., the publication date of the collection – in the data citation element. This could be a problem because:

- this date is missing in the metadata
- it is not clear which kind of date the citation is referring to

The Published Date is in fact the issued date of the DRI object, and it is part of the collection metadata. For example, in <https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/5999t182s> the published date is 2015-06-25 while the collection objects date ranges from 1933 to 2013 (Creation Date).

The creation date is found in the *dcterms:created* field and also in the *dcterms:temporal* field (DCMI coverage qualification corresponds to the metadata label “Subject (Temporal)” in the DRI). Therefore, every object member of the collection inherits the published date from the collection it belongs to, but this relationship is not made evident.

We propose to associate the published date to the Distributor (or *edm:dataProvider* with its own role, e.g., “Depositing Institution”) in the citation, hence changing “Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor]” to “Digital Repository of Ireland (<date> [Distributor]”. For example, “Digital Repository of Ireland (2015) [Distributor]” or “Contemporary Music Centre (2015) [Depositing Institution]”. Alternatively, the date can be related to the collection adding “[part of] <collection title> <collection identifier> (2015)” at the end of the citation. Furthermore, this will help to clarify the collection data model.

5.3.1 Use cases

Use case name	Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey
Example object <i>The example object to review.</i> The URL of the example object (PID preferable).	https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Text Sound (Image)
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Scores < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300026427 > Sound recordings < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028633 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	56 %, https://f-uji.net/view/402 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i> The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool .	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329
Citation record	Mulvey, Gráinne, & Contemporary Music Centre. (2015) Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Contemporary

<p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The default citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>Music Centre [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329</p>
---	--

Table 8: Use case 1 of DRI case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

Issues reported by DRI: single DOI for different assets, no indication in citation as to format or rights.

The elements included in the citation are not sufficiently comprehensive for the identification and attribution of the cultural heritage object.

Creators field doesn't use persistent identifiers, so the creator PIDs are not included in the data citation.

The relationship with the internal/source identifier "CMCMULVEY001" (value of "dc:identifier") of the object is not clear. This identifier is also found in the RDF metadata, but it is not included in the DOI DataCite metadata.

The information on the cultural heritage object represented is missing. The 'Akanos' opera, of which the digital object <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329> constitutes a fragment in the form of both a musical score (as a native digital object) and an orchestral recording, is the cultural heritage object.

The data citation should highlight the composite nature of the digital object, for instance by adding the resource type (e.g., using "Dataset" or "Image and Audio") from a controlled vocabulary. In the search facet at the collection level, the "Music score" resource type is faceted as "Text" whereas the example object metadata contains <dc:type>Image</dc:type> and <dc:type>Music Score</dc:type>.

One way to differentiate the resource types in the data citation can be to make use of the special character '#' in the DOI of the object. DOI supports "#" in the redirecting functionality; for example, to refer to the audio file it is possible to build a URL like <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329#/files/95944s78g/>. A "split citation" button could be implemented, to get the two data citations with the different formats (and maybe rights).

The relationship with the collection the object belongs to is found in the RDF metadata "dc:isPartOf <<https://repository.dri.ie/catalog/5999t182s#id>>" but not embedded in the Dublin Core full metadata (which, if we understand correctly, corresponds to the source metadata provided by the depositing institution). As stated above, this is relevant information that should be exposed in the CHO citation.

Rights can change, so we don't report them in the citation.

Proposed citation

[Mulvey, Gráinne](#), & [Contemporary Music Centre](#). Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey, Digital Repository of Ireland (2015) [Distributor], Contemporary Music Centre [Depositing Institution], <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329> (
[has part] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329#/files/95944578g/> (Sound);
[has part] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999vs329#/files/5999vs33k/> (Text);
[part of] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.5999t182s>;
[sample of] [[Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey](#) (ISWC T-030.145.092-9)];
)

Use case name	Collection: Fáilte Ireland Tourism Collection
Example objects <i>The example objects to review.</i> The URL of the example objects (PID preferable).	https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.8336wk645 https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.d7926o89j
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Image
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Plasterwork < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300015343 > Black-and-white photographs < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300128347 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	60 %, https://www.f-uji.net/view/403 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i> The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool .	Not available https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=10.7486/DRI.8336wk645 https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=10.7486/DRI.d7926o89j
Citation record <i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i>	Fáilte Ireland. (2020) 20 Lower Dominick Street, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Dublin City Library and Archive [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.d7926o89j

The default citation record of the example object.	Fáilte Ireland. (2020) 20 Lower Dominick Street, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Dublin City Library and Archive [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.8336wk645
--	---

Table 9: Use case 2 of DRI case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

Issues reported by DRI: lack of granularity in citation, not possible to distinguish by description/title, no indication in citation as to format or rights, same info but different DOI.

The elements included in the citation are not exhaustive enough for the identification and citation attribution of the cultural heritage object. Creators field doesn't use persistent identifiers, so the creator PIDs are not included in the data citation.

The information on the cultural heritage object represented, i.e. the 18th-century plasterwork, is missing.

With regard to the problem of the indistinguishable citation, it should be emphasised that the two subjects are different and that the photo was taken in the same year. This issue is the opposite of the "Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey" use case. We suggest creating a collection that groups objects with identical metadata, and adding the relationship to the collection in the data citation. Alternatively, looking at the "Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey" case, a composite object can be created, with the advantage of the same type of object (Image), a single DOI assigned and, as done in the "Akanos by Gráinne Mulvey" use case, the reference to the file inserted via the # after the DOI URL. A further advantage is that the nature of the cultural objects represented is the same, therefore this can be made explicit in the citation.

Proposed citation

[Fáilte Ireland](#). 20 Lower Dominick Street, Digital Repository of Ireland (2020) [Distributor], Dublin City Library and Archive [Depositing Institution], <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.8336wk645> (Image) ([part of] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.pk02rr951-1>; [image of] [Houses, [20 Lower Dominick Street](#), Dublin];)

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>Transport Infrastructure Ireland, Digital Heritage College</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.vq28c740x-3</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dataset</p> <p>Text</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Radiocarbon dating</p> <p><http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300054717></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p><i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i></p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>56 %, https://www.f-ujl.net/view/404 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p> <p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	<p>Not available</p> <p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=10.7486/DRI.vq28c740x-3</p>
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>Transport Infrastructure Ireland. (2019) Radiocarbon dates, A056 N22 Tralee Bypass Radiocarbon Dates Catalogue, County Kerry, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Transport Infrastructure Ireland (TII) [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.vq28c740x-3</p>

The default citation record of the example object.	
--	--

Table 10: Use case 3 of DRI case study.

Analysis and suggested improvements

Issues reported by DRI: granularity in citation, no indication in citation as to format.

The data citation is missing the object collection or subcollection it belongs to. Since the RDF representation contains the relationship to the subcollection “Archaeological Excavation Reports” and the collection usually refers to the Depositing Institution, it may be useful to include the subcollection in the data citation. For example, we can expand the citation adding ‘dc:isPartOf “<collection name>” <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v9807h80j-3>’. The object would then be cited as the following:

Proposed citation

[Transport Infrastructure Ireland](#). Radiocarbon dates, A056 N22 Tralee Bypass Radiocarbon Dates Catalogue, County Kerry, Digital Repository of Ireland (2019) [Distributor], Transport Infrastructure Ireland (TII) [Depositing Institution], <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.vq28c740x-3> (Dataset) ([part of] <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.v9807h80j-3>; [analysis of] [N22 Tralee Bypass, [Kerry](#), [Ireland](#)];)

6. Phaidra - University of Padua: Case study

Phaidra (Permanent Hosting, Archiving and Indexing of Digital Resources and Assets) is the University of Padua Library System’s platform for long-term archiving of digital collections. Phaidra hosts various types of digital objects (antiquarian books, manuscripts, photographs, wallcharts, maps, learning objects, films, archive material and museum objects).

Phaidra offers a search facility to identify specific objects, and each object can be viewed, downloaded, used and reused to the extent permitted by law and by its associated licences.

The objects in the digital collections on the Phaidra platform are sourced from libraries (in large part due to the digitisation projects promoted by the Library System itself), museums and archives at the University of Padua and other institutions, including the Ca’ Foscari University and the Università Iuav in Venice.

Description of the research data repository from its [re3data.org record](https://re3data.org/record/).

6.1 General

<p>Repository Name</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryName - The full name of the research data repository.</i></p>	Phaidra - University of Padua
<p>Repository URL</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryUrl - The URL of the research data repository.</i></p>	https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/
<p>Repository identifier</p> <p><i>r3d:repositoryIdentifier - A globally unique identifier that refers to the research data repository or a record describing the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The URI of the research data repository identifier (DOI, ROR, RRID, Handle, etc.).</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.25430/phaidra</p> <p>https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q106692828</p>
<p>Repositories registry records</p> <p>The URLs of the research data repository record in the re3data.org, FAIRsharing.org, OpenDOAR repositories registry.</p>	<p>re3data.org: http://doi.org/10.17616/R31NJMHU</p> <p>FAIRsharing.org: https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.692301</p> <p>OpenDOAR: http://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/id/repository/4368</p>

<p>Provider type</p> <p><i>r3d:providerType - The type of provider.</i></p>	<p>Data provider</p> <p>Service provider</p>
<p>Data provider for aggregator/catalogue</p> <p><i>The aggregator or catalogue services the research data repository provides the research data.</i></p> <p>Catalogue/aggregator name and catalogue/aggregator home page URL, or Unknown.</p>	<p>Europeana <https://www.europeana.eu></p> <p>Culturaitalia <https://www.culturaitalia.it/></p> <p>Internet Archive <https://archive.org/></p> <p>CorrespSearch <https://correspsearch.net/></p>
<p>Subjects</p> <p><i>r3d:subject - The disciplinary focus of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Humanities and Social Science</p> <p>History of Science</p> <p>Geography</p> <p>History</p> <p>Historical linguistics</p> <p>Natural Science</p>
<p>Persistent identifier systems</p> <p><i>r3d:pidSystem - The persistent identifier system that is used/provided by the research data repository for research data.</i></p> <p>The PID systems provided by the research data repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DOI ● Handle ● ARK ● PURL ● URN ● Other (provide related URL) <p>Provide also the registration authority (if known).</p>	<p>Handle</p>
<p>Policy</p> <p><i>r3d:policy - Policies providing information concerning the usage of the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>Phaidra - University of Padua Preservation Plan <https://bibliotecadigitale.cab.unipd.it/en/digital-library/digital-repositories/digital-preservation></p>

<p>The policy title and URL of the data curation policy, sustainability policy, data quality policy, etc.</p> <p>The data citation policy should be stated in the "Data Citation" section of the template.</p>	
<p>Repository certification</p> <p><i>r3d:certificate</i> - The certificate, accreditation or standard the research data repository complies with.</p> <p>The certificate name, URL, year of accreditation and validity period.</p>	<p>CoreTrustSeal <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Phaidra-at-the-Library-System-of-the-University-of-Padova.pdf>, 2019. Expired (valid until 2022-11-13).</p>
<p>Data model</p> <p>Brief description of the data model and/or related documentation URL.</p>	<p>The digital objects hosted by Phaidra can belong to the following content types: Collection, Image, Book, PDF Document, Video, Audio, Web Resource, Other (assets).</p> <p>The metadata schemas used are Universität Wien metadata model (abridged UWmetadata) - an application profile of Standard Learning Object Metadata (LOM) - and PHAIDRA DC Metadata Element Set. The two metadata schemas include descriptive, technical and administrative metadata elements.</p> <p>Phaidra objects can be linked using the supported relationships system, which is serialized in RDF/XML syntax in the object's internal metadata managed by the Fedora platform. Objects can be aggregated into collections using the "hasCollectionMember" relationship.</p> <p>Phaidra is transitioning to an RDF data model which has already been designed but not yet implemented in the repository.</p> <p>Documentation: https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/info/impressum#metadata</p>
<p>Resource types</p> <p><i>r3d:contentType</i> - All types of resources available in the research data repository.</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1.</p>	<p>Image <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_513></p> <p>Sound <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_18cc></p> <p>Video <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_12ce></p> <p>Text <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_18cf></p> <p>Other <http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_1843></p>

<p>Metadata standards</p> <p><i>r3d:metadataStandard - The metadata standard the research data repository complies with.</i></p> <p>Standard name and URI from the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (preferable) or the Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications, or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Dublin Core <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15></p> <p>Other - University of Vienna Metadata <https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/static/phaidra-uwmetadata.pdf></p> <p>Other - ICCD Cataloguing Standard <https://github.com/ICCD-MiBACT/Standard-catalografici/tree/master/schede-di-catalogo></p>
<p>Object landing page metadata qualification</p> <p><i>Machine-readable metadata provided in the object landing page of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Possible values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schema.org • Dublin Core • EPrints metadata • Highwire Press metadata • Open Graph metadata • Signposting Typed Links • Other (provide related URL) 	<p>Schema.org</p> <p>Dublin Core</p> <p>Signposting Typed Links</p>
<p>Semantic artefacts integration</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefacts the research data repository supports in the object's metadata.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>VIAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/2053></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p> <p>LCNAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/18536></p> <p>GND <http://bartoc.org/en/node/430></p> <p>Other - ISNI <https://isni.org/page/search-database/></p>
<p>Versioning</p> <p><i>r3d:versioning - The research data repository supports versioning of research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Data access rights</p>	<p>embargoed access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_f1cf></p>

<p><i>r3d:dataAccessType</i> - The access regulation to the research data sets provided by the research data repository.</p> <p>Term and URI from COAR Access Rights Vocabulary 1.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>metadata only access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_14cb></p> <p>open access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2></p>
<p>Data rights</p> <p><i>The applicable rights to the research data in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI of data rights available in the research data repository from the RightsStatements.org list or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>In Copyright <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/></p>
<p>Data licences</p> <p><i>r3d:dataLicense</i> - The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for research data.</p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX Licence List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>GNU General Public License v3.0 or later <https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html></p> <p>CC BY 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-SA 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-ND 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-ND-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC-ND 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0.html></p> <p>CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-NC-SA-4.0.html></p> <p>Other - CC BY 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0/it/deed.en></p> <p>Other - CC BY-SA 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/it/deed.en></p> <p>Other - CC BY-NC 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/2.0/it/deed.en></p> <p>Other - CC BY-ND 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nd/2.0/it/deed.en></p>

	<p>Other - CC BY-NC-ND 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/2.0/it/deed.en></p> <p>Other - CC BY-NC-SA 2.0 IT <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/2.0/it/deed.en></p>
<p>Metadata licences</p> <p><i>The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for the research objects metadata.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX License List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Same as <i>Data licences</i> value.</p>

Table 11: General section of Phaidra case study.

6.2 Data Citation

Phaidra - University of Padua does not provide a data citation policy, nor does it provide a data citation feature and records.

<p>Data citation policy</p> <p><i>r3d:citationGuidelineUrl - The URL of the policy outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>Endorsed data citation recommendations</p> <p><i>Data citation recommendations the repository endorses in the data citation policy.</i></p> <p>Data citation recommendation title and URL.</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>“Cite as” feature</p> <p><i>An automatic feature the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p>	<p>Not applicable</p>
<p>Data citation styles</p>	<p>Not applicable</p>

<p><i>The citation styles the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>Available citation styles in the "Cite as" feature of the research data repository, and the citation style tools implemented (e.g. Citation Style Language processor "citeproc-js").</p>	
<p>Data citation record elements</p> <p><i>Critical citation elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Citation element and citation element property in the citation record.</p>	Not applicable
<p>Data citation record syntax</p> <p><i>The data citation record format the research data repository provides to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>The element names comprised in the data citation record in the format and order the research data repository provides.</p>	Not applicable
<p>Data citation record semantics</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefact elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	Not applicable

Table 12: Data Citation section of Phaidra case study.

6.3 Findings and Discussion

Phaidra - University of Padua does not currently support a citation model. We have therefore identified a core set of critical citation elements that are functional for the citation of the digital objects distributed by the repository.

The elements are taken from the current data model – based on UWmetadata and PHAIDRA_DC metadata schemas (see “Data Model” above) – and the forthcoming [Phaidra RDF Data Model](#) not yet implemented in the repository. The RDF data model has been designed in collaboration with the Phaidra team at the University of Vienna. The RDF data model has already been implemented in the [Phaidra - University of Vienna digital repository](#).

For each citation element, we provide a brief description and the associated property in the citation record (mandatory, recommended, optional, system-generated). These properties are related to the metadata schema: the corresponding field could be mandatory (sometimes system-generated) or optional but recommended: in the citation model all the proposed element are considered mandatory, but some of them may not exist in the digital object metadata.

Our focus is on the semantics of the elements, for example through the provision of persistent identifiers that can be associated with the element. We do not get into the nitty-gritty of the syntax of the element in the citation.

The process of selecting, identifying and describing key citation elements is intended as an opening step towards the design of a comprehensive Phaidra - University of Padua citation model, to be carried out in coherence with the ongoing development of the project.

6.3.1 Critical citation elements

Actors name & actors PID [Mandatory]

Actors are all the entities included in the descriptive metadata of the digital objects, in particular those identified as authors.

PID = persistent identifier of the entity (e.g., VIAF, Wikidata ID, ORCID)

Title [Mandatory]

The title of the digital object.

[Part of] Collection title & collection PID [Recommended]

Collection is a Phaidra resource type. Phaidra objects are usually aggregated into collections, which are themselves digital objects with metadata and a persistent identifier but without an associated byte stream. Collections often provide the context for the objects they contained.

Collection Title = the title of the collection object.

Collection PID = persistent identifier of the collection object (Handle).

Resource type [Mandatory]

The resource type of the digital object (e.g., terms from the [COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1](#), for example, “Image”).

Type of object [Recommended]

The object type (e.g., terms from the [Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus](#), for example, “Manuscripts”). The object type field is described in the [Phaidra RDF Data Model](#).

Date issued [Mandatory, System-generated]

The date of deposit of the digital object in the repository.

Date created timespan [Recommended]

The creation date of the cultural heritage object described in the digital object.

Location [Recommended]

Location of the cultural heritage object described in the digital object. For example, the call number and the physical location described by the `bf:shelfMark` and `bf:physicalLocation` properties in the [Phaidra RDF Data Model](#).

PID [Mandatory, System-generated]

The persistent identifier of the digital object (Handle identifier).

[Relationship to the CHO] CHO title & CHO PID [Recommended]

CHO title = title of the cultural heritage object

CHO PID = if available, the persistent identifier of the cultural heritage object. For instance, ISMI for manuscripts, ISWC for musical works, Getty Cultural Objects Name Authority (CONA) for works of art, or a locally-generated PID comprising an institution PID (e.g., ISIL) and a call number, e.g., “<https://doi.org/<base-ch>/ISIL-IT-PD0341-Ar.54>”.

Publisher/Host (Publisher/Host Name & Publisher/Host PID) [Mandatory, System-generated]

The data repository that publishes and hosts the digital object.

PID = the persistent identifier associated with the data repository (DOI). For example, [Phaidra - University of Padua](#) [Distributor].

6.3.2 Citation record example

Actors name & actors PID

Title

Publisher/Host Name & Publisher/Host PID [Distributor] (Date issued)

PID [Resource type]

[part of] Collection Title & Collection PID

[relationship to the CHO] CHO Title & CHO PID (Date created timespan) [Location of the CHO]

[Type of object]

6.3.3 Use cases

Use case name	“Vocabolario di tre nobilissimi linguaggi italiano...”
Example object <i>The example object to review.</i> The URL of the example object (PID preferable).	https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.497845
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Text Book
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Manuscripts (documents) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028569 > Dictionaries < https://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300026186 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	75 %, https://f-uji.net/view/396 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i> The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool .	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.497845
Citation record	Not applicable

<p>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	
---	--

Table 13: Use case 1 of Phaidra case study.

Analysis

Volume 1 of: *Vocabolario di tre nobilissimi linguaggi italiano, illirico, e latino [...]*. This work was written in Zadar by Canon Giovanni Tanzlingher at the end of the 17th century, at a time of crisis and cultural stagnation in the Dalmatian-Croatian area, then still heavily threatened by the Turks. Through this work, the author intended to remedy the corruption of the Croatian (or, as it was called at the time, Illyrian) language, steeped in Italianisms, by demonstrating how rich and vital it was, thus ultimately promoting a cultural reawakening among the population. No less than four copies of this work have come down to us. One is kept in Zagreb, at the Archives of the Croatian Academy (shelfmark Ib-142), another in Zadar at the Chapter Library of the Cathedral of St. Anastasia (shelfmark 2891), the third in London, at the British Library (shelfmark 10,360). The last copy is kept in Padua: it belonged for a long time to the Library of the former Institute of Slavic Philology (shelfmark VII a 1-2), and is currently kept in the Beato Pellegrino Library (shelfmark ANT.E.XVIII.g.1 and ANT.E.XVIII.g.2).

The Padua copy (two folio volumes bound in parchment) is by far the most extensive and best-preserved of those that have come down to us, all of which have remained unpublished and thus practically unused until today. In its 1316 pages, it presents over 80,000 Croatian lexical units, many of which do not appear in the Rječnik hrvatskoga ili srpskoga jezika (ARj) published by the Yugoslav Academy. These entries cover a wide range of fields: the public and private spheres, the religious sphere, public administration, construction, agriculture, etc.

Proposed citation

[Tanzlingher Zanotti, Ivan \(Giovanni\)](#)

Volume Primo

[PHAIDRA - University of Padua](#) [Distributor] (2023)

<https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.497845> [Text, Book]

[part of] [Vocabolario di tre nobilissimi linguaggi italiano, illirico, e latino con \[...\]](#)

[digital representation of] *Volume Primo [del] Vocabolario di tre nobilissimi linguaggi italiano, illirico, e latino con l'agg:ta di molt'erbe semplici, e termini militari raccolto dal molto reverendo signor D. Giovanni Tanzlingher dottor, e canonico di Zara dedicato (1699-1704)* [Biblioteca Beato Pellegrino: ANT.E.XVIII.g.1] [Manuscripts (documents), Dictionaries]

Use case name	Erbario farmaceutico di Fra Giorgio
Example object <i>The example object to review.</i> The URL of the example object (PID preferable).	https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332589
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Other - Collection
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Manuscripts (documents) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028569 > Herbaria (documents) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300440768 > Natural history specimens < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379591 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	43 %, https://f-uji.net/view/411 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i> The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool .	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332589
Citation record	Not applicable

<p>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	
---	--

Table 14: Use case 2 of Phaidra case study.

Analysis

The collection consists of individual verso and recto (i.e. back and front) images of the leaves of the paper manuscript *Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730*, each with its own unique descriptive metadata and PIDs. The manuscript contains a total of 240 dried botanical specimens belonging to around 220 species, bound into a volume of approximately 80 leaves.

Dried plants are glued on the right-hand page (*recto*), while on the left-hand page (*verso*) there is a handwritten text with the names of the specimens and their properties, particularly from a medical-pharmaceutical point of view.

The collection itself is part of a larger collection dedicated to the illustrated herbaria of the Library of the Botanical Garden of Padua. It is a digital collection created to better organise the contents of the repository and does not correspond to a physical collection.

The citation may be made either at the level of the manuscript (i.e. the collection) or at the level of the individual folios. When citing folios, the collection needs to be referenced.

Proposed citation

Fra Giorgio da Venezia

Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730

[PHAIDRA - University of Padua](#) [Distributor] (2017)

<https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332589> [Collection]

[part of] [Erbari illustrati della biblioteca dell'Orto botanico di Padova](#)

[digital representation of] *Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730 (1730)* [Biblioteca dell'Orto Botanico - Ar.54] [Manuscripts (documents), Herbaria (documents), Natural history specimens]

Use case name	Lepidio, Consolida, Consolida Regale
Example object <i>The example object to review.</i> The URL of the example object (PID preferable).	https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332593
Resource type Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).	Image Book part
Object type Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).	Manuscripts (documents) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028569 > Herbaria (documents) < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300440768 > Natural history specimens < http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300379591 >
Automated FAIRness assessment <i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i> Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool .	72 %, https://f-uji.net/view/419 (F-UJI 2.2.5)
Automated citation metadata <i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i> The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool .	https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332593
Citation record	Not applicable

<p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The full citation record of the example object.</p>	
--	--

Table 15: Use case 3 of Phaidra case study.

Analysis

An individual verso and recto (i.e. back and front) image of the leaves of the paper manuscript *Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730*.

The title of the object is derived from the plants presented on the page, the description contains scientific and current names of the plants.

With a view to information integration, the title provided by the name of the plant represented can be semantically specified by the *[is about]* relation linked to the GBIF taxon ID.

Unlike the previous use case, for this object the fact that it belongs to the collection is very important because it represents its context and provenance.

Proposed citation

Lepidio, Consolida, Consolida Regale

[PHAIDRA - University of Padua](#) [Distributor] (2017)

<https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.332593> [Image, Book part]

[is about] [Lepidium latifolium L.](#), [Consolida regalis S.F. Gray cv.](#)

[part of] [Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730](#)

[image of] *Erbario farmaceutico c. 1730* (1730) [Biblioteca dell'Orto Botanico - Ar.54] [Manuscripts (documents), Herbaria (documents), Natural history specimens]

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>Bozzetto studio per il monumento "Resistenza e Liberazione" di Jannis Kounellis</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.535272</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Image</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>Bozzetti <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300047838></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p><i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i></p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>75 %, https://f-uji.net/view/420 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p> <p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	<p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.535272</p>
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>Not applicable</p>

The full citation record of the example object.	
---	--

Table 16: Use case 4 of Phaidra case study.

Analysis

Watercolour and India ink sketch on Fabriano paper by Jannis Kounellis, part of the preliminary study project for the "Resistenza e Liberazione" (Resistance and Liberation) monument, consisting of wooden boards of different sizes arranged horizontally and the Italian flag on the left.

Proposed citation

[Kounellis, Jannis](#)

Jannis Kounellis - bozzetto studio per il monumento "Resistenza e Liberazione"

[PHAIDRA - University of Padua](#) [Distributor] (2023)

<https://hdl.handle.net/11168/11.535272> [Image]

[part of] [Jannis Kounellis - bozzetti dell'opera "Monumento alla memoria di Concetto Marchesi, Egidio Meneghetti ed Ezio Franceschini", più conosciuta con il titolo "Resistenza e Liberazione"](#)

[digital representation of] *Bozzetto studio per il monumento "Resistenza e Liberazione" (1994)*
[Archivio generale, Patrimonio culturale multitematico, n. 328] [Bozzetti]

Annexes

CHO Citation Elements. Repository Case Studies. Template

One of the activities of the project *A FAIR-enabling citation model for Cultural Heritage Objects* involved the in-depth analysis of citation practices of selected data repositories as case studies. A case study template was developed to this purpose.

The template comprises several descriptors intended to identify the studied data repository, the repository data citation practices along with one or more examples of citation records of objects – hosted by the repository – as use cases.

We use the namespace `r3d` = "<http://www.re3data.org/schema/3-1>" in the descriptors.

General

This section of the template aims at the identification of the data repository, and the description of the model and metadata of the digital objects it hosts.

Repository Name <i>r3d:repositoryName - The full name of the research data repository.</i>	E.g.: Phaidra - University of Padua
Repository URL <i>r3d:repositoryUrl - The URL of the research data repository.</i>	E.g.: https://phaidra.cab.unipd.it/
Repository identifier <i>r3d:repositoryIdentifier - A globally unique identifier that refers to the research data repository or a record describing the research data repository.</i> The URI of the research data repository identifier (DOI, ROR, RRID, Handle, etc.).	E.g.: https://doi.org/10.25430/phaidra
Repositories registry records The URLs of the research data repository record in the re3data.org , FAIRsharing.org , OpenDOAR repositories registry.	re3data.org: URL FAIRsharing.org: URL OpenDOAR: URL
Provider type	Data provider / Service provider

<p><i>r3d:providerType</i> - The type of provider.</p>	
<p>Data provider for aggregator/catalogue</p> <p><i>The aggregator or catalogue services the research data repository provides the research data.</i></p> <p>Catalogue/aggregator name and catalogue/aggregator home page URL, or Unknown.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Europeana <https://www.europeana.eu></p> <p>ARIADNE <https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/></p> <p>OpenAIRE <https://www.openaire.eu/></p> <p>EOSC Marketplace and Portal <https://eosc-portal.eu/></p>
<p>Subjects</p> <p><i>r3d:subject</i> - The disciplinary focus of the research data repository.</p> <p>Term from the FAIRsharing Subject Ontology or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Humanities and Social Science</p> <p>Art</p>
<p>Persistent identifier systems</p> <p><i>r3d:pidSystem</i> - The persistent identifier system that is used/provided by the research data repository for research data.</p> <p>The PID systems provided by the research data repository:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DOI ● Handle ● ARK ● PURL ● URN ● Other (provide related URL) <p>Provide also the registration authority (if known).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>ARK</p> <p>DOI (Datacite, Crossref, Medra)</p> <p>Handle</p>
<p>Policy</p> <p><i>r3d:policy</i> - Policies providing information concerning the usage of the research data repository.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Phaidra - University of Padua Preservation Plan <https://bibliotecadigitale.cab.unipd.it/en/digital-library/digital-repositories/digital-preservation></p> <p>DPLA Metadata Quality Guidelines</p>

<p>The policy title and URL of the data curation policy, sustainability policy, data quality policy, etc.</p> <p>The data citation policy should be stated in the "Data Citation" section of the template.</p>	<p><http://bit.ly/dpla-metadata-qual></p>
<p>Repository certification</p> <p><i>r3d:certificate - The certificate, accreditation or standard the research data repository complies with.</i></p> <p>The certificate name, URL, year of accreditation and validity period.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>CoreTrustSeal <https://www.coretrustseal.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Phaidra-at-the-Library-System-of-the-University-of-Padova.pdf>, 2019</p>
<p>Data model</p> <p>Brief description of the data model and/or related documentation URL.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Phaidra data model is... https://phaidra.univie.ac.at/metadata-fields-help</p>
<p>Resource types</p> <p><i>r3d:contentType - All types of resources available in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Image Sound Video Text Other (e.g. 3D Object)</p>
<p>Metadata standards</p> <p><i>r3d:metadataStandard - The metadata standard the research data repository complies with.</i></p> <p>Standard name and URI from the RDA Metadata Standards Catalog (preferable) or the Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications, or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Dublin Core <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15> MODS <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m97> DataCite Metadata Schema <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m11> CIDOC CRM <https://bartoc.org/en/node/1644></p>
<p>Object landing page metadata qualification</p> <p><i>Machine-readable metadata provided in the object landing page of the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Schema.org Dublin Core Signposting Typed Links</p>

<p>Possible values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schema.org • Dublin Core • EPrints metadata • Highwire Press metadata • Open Graph metadata • Signposting Typed Links • Other (provide related URL) 	
<p>Semantic artefacts integration</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefacts the research data repository supports in the object's metadata.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>VIAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/2053></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p> <p>Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus <http://bartoc.org/en/node/75></p>
<p>Versioning</p> <p><i>r3d:versioning - The research data repository supports versioning of research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes / No / Unknown</p>
<p>Data access rights</p> <p><i>r3d:dataAccessType - The access regulation to the research data sets provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI from COAR Access Rights Vocabulary 1.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>embargoed access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_f1cf></p> <p>metadata only access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_14cb></p> <p>open access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2></p> <p>restricted access <http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_16ec></p>
<p>Data rights</p> <p><i>The applicable rights to the research data in the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Term and URI of data rights available in the research data repository from the RightsStatements.org list or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>In Copyright <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC/1.0/></p> <p>In Copyright - Educational Use Permitted <http://rightsstatements.org/vocab/InC-EDU/1.0/></p>

<p>Data licences</p> <p><i>r3d:dataLicense - The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for research data.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX Licence List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.html></p> <p>Open Data Commons Attribution License v1.0 <https://spdx.org/licenses/ODC-By-1.0.html></p> <p>GNU General Public License v3.0 or later <https://spdx.org/licenses/GPL-3.0-or-later.html></p>
<p>Metadata licences</p> <p><i>The license or licensing scheme the research data repository offers for the research objects metadata.</i></p> <p>License name and URI from the SPDX License List or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creative Commons Zero v1.0 Universal <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0.html></p>

Annex table 1: General section of the template.

Data Citation

This section aims at outlining the descriptors related to the citation-specific policies, features and citation model provided by the research data repository.

<p>Data citation policy</p> <p><i>r3d:citationGuidelineUrl - The URL of the policy outlining how to cite research data provided by the research data repository.</i></p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.rx91h486p</p>
<p>Endorsed data citation recommendations</p> <p><i>Data citation recommendations the repository endorses in the data citation policy.</i></p> <p>Data citation recommendation title and URL.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Data Citation Synthesis Group: Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles. FORCE11 <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egykh></p> <p>Heritage Data Reuse Charter <https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/></p> <p>CODATA-ICSTI Task Group on Data Citation Standards and Practices, "Out of Cite, Out of Mind: The Current State of Practice, Policy, and Technology for the Citation of Data" <https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/dsj/12/0/12_OSOM13-043/_pdf></p>
<p>"Cite as" feature</p> <p><i>An automatic feature the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p>	<p>Yes / No / Unknown</p>
<p>Data citation styles</p> <p><i>The citation styles the research data repository provides in order to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>Available citation styles in the "Cite as" feature of the research data repository, and the citation style tools implemented (e.g. Citation Style Language processor "citeproc-js").</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>APA, MLA, Chicago - via citeproc-js CSL processor.</p>
<p>Data citation record elements</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Title [Mandatory]</p>

<p><i>Critical citation elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>Citation element and citation element property in the citation record.</p>	<p>Creator [Mandatory]</p> <p>PID [Mandatory]</p> <p>Publisher [Optional]</p>
<p>Data citation record syntax</p> <p><i>The data citation record format the research data repository provides to cite the research data.</i></p> <p>The element names comprised in the data citation record in the format and order the research data repository provides.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Creator (Publication Date) Title, Publisher, Distributor Name [Distributor], Depositing Institution Name [Depositing Institution]. DOI</p>
<p>Data citation record semantics</p> <p><i>The Semantic artefact elements provided in the data citation record of the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The name of the semantic artefact and its URI (preferable: URI from Bartoc.org - Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications) or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>ORCID <https://bartoc.org/en/node/2021></p> <p>VIAF <http://bartoc.org/en/node/2053></p> <p>Wikidata QID <http://bartoc.org/en/node/1940></p> <p>Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus <http://bartoc.org/en/node/75></p>

Annex table 2: Data Citation section of the template.

Use case

Analysis of the citation record of a sample digital object. It also comprises an automated FAIRness assessment of the digital object. This section is intended to be duplicated for each analysed digital object.

<p>Use case name</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Adults and Lifelong Learning</p>
<p>Example object</p> <p><i>The example object to review.</i></p> <p>The URL of the example object (PID preferable).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9s16ds12f</p>
<p>Resource type</p> <p>Term from COAR Resource Types Vocabulary 3.1 or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Image</p> <p>Video</p>
<p>Object type</p> <p>Term from Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus or Other (provide related URL).</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>Scores <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300026427></p> <p>Sound recordings <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300028633></p>
<p>Automated FAIRness assessment</p> <p><i>The FAIRness assessment of the research object provided by an automated FAIR data assessment tool.</i></p> <p>Score and URL of the automated FAIRness assessment achieved in the F-UJI FAIR Data Assessment tool.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>60 %, https://f-uji.net/view/422 (F-UJI 2.2.5)</p>
<p>Automated citation metadata</p> <p><i>The object metadata retrieved by an automated citation tool.</i></p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>https://v4e-lab.isti.cnr.it/citview/demo/index.html?schema_url=https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9S16DS12F</p>

<p>The URL of the automated citation metadata retrieved by the Citation Metadata Viewer Demo tool.</p>	
<p>Citation record</p> <p><i>The citation record provided by the research data repository.</i></p> <p>The default citation record of the example object.</p>	<p>E.g.:</p> <p>National Museum of Ireland. (2019) Adults and Lifelong Learning, Digital Repository of Ireland [Distributor], Arts and Culture in Education Research Repository [Depositing Institution], https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.9516ds12f</p>

Annex table 3: Use case section of the template.